

UOT 008:002.6

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THE ROLE OF NATIONAL SELF-AWARENESS AND INFORMATION EXCHANGE IN THE COMMUNICATION PROCESS

Abstract. Azerbaijan has entered a new social, political and economic structure as an independent state, many changes have taken place in its cultural life and the stage of flexible democratic activity has begun in the last thirty years. Especially, the predominance of democratic principles in the new society has expanded the boundaries of relations between people and revealed the necessity of innovation in the form and essence of cultural communication. These changes in the socio-political and cultural life of Azerbaijan have also changed the socio-psychological nature of the communication. The emergence of a new society and the democratic principles it gave to people led to the elimination of existing restrictions in the field of cultural communication. It was the elimination of these restrictions that created a moral ground for wider use of universal cultural resources, revealed the relevance of the problems of restoring cultural communication from historical and traditional aspects. It turns out that people's forms of national, religious communication and other spiritual values, which have developed over the centuries, are of great upbringing importance and create essentially a new socio-psychological basis for the expansion of cultural communication between people in the modern era.

Key words: communication, sociability, information exchange, interaction, self-awareness.

Introduction. The adaptation of social life to the requirements of the market economy has also changed the socio-psychological nature of the cultural communication. For this reason, there are acute contradictions between

the democratic principles of the new society and the concept of cultural development inherited from the communist Soviet regime. Especially, the concept of communist culture and moral principles did not give the cultural and educational institutions of our country opportunity to use examples of world culture widely. The problem of eliminating these restrictions, wider using universal resources, restoring historical and traditional aspects of cultural communication is of great importance today. Now it can be boldly said that the forms of national, religious communication and other spiritual values created and developed by people over the centuries have maintained their relevance in the field of upbringing system, and they created a socio-psychological basis for the expansion of cultural communication between people in the modern era.

The change of the state structure and its socio-political environment has actualized the development of new scientific-theoretical bases of cultural communication tools. At the same time, the study of international examples and the use of various cultural means of communication in our country confirm its scientific relevance once again in order to integrate Azerbaijan into the world culture. So, today, keeping the national culture alive, developing and transmitting it to future generations should be the main duty of every culturologist.

The interpretation of the main material. The concept of “communication” includes a specific type of social relations, especially “subject-object” relations. Not only the influence of one subject on another, but also the processes of their interaction, perception and relations are revealed in the course of the analysis of these relations [4, p. 83].

One of the main reasons why people communicate with each other is related to the need to acquire different relevant information. Information exchange has occupied a special place in human society and has become one of the main means of communication and rapprochement between people since ancient times. The sophists who lived in the 5th century BC tried to associate the effect of information exchange on sociability with the communication process, albeit in an abstract way. Although in a simple form, they divided communication into three important aspects. According to these aspects:

1. It consists of relationships between people and their interaction;
2. Communicative relations formed between people are formed wilfully, accidentally, in fact, it depends on the environment, circumstances and is related to certain reasons;

3. Communicative relation is not only beneficial for both sides. One of the sides may suffer more or less damage from this relationship [5].

At the same time, according to the ancient Greek philosopher Socrates, communication also helps a human's self-awareness and guides him to a guaranteed degree. The occurrence of the communication process depends on the feelings and behavior of the two sides who want to exchange information. Of course, there is a collection of opinions and information in both of them, and the sides can discover these opinions and information by communicating with each other. Both sides become the object and the subject of communication in such a situation. Information exchange can be in individual or group form from a socio-psychological point of view. However, both sides inform each other sufficiently regardless of minority or majority. The second main point of this process is the availability of common means of communication that both sides can use, i.e. the communicating sides take information not from each other, but from a specific source known to both of them. This source can be a library, a documentary, a speaker, a reviewer, etc. In any case, a common information center gives both individuals opportunity to be informed at the same time and place. The received information is discussed and becomes an exchange material. Especially, the complexity of the information during the communication process needs to be reinterpreted. This process increases the continuity of communication and at the same time facilitates the comprehension of information.

Unfortunately, the essence of information exchange in communication has not been widely studied from the aspect of pedagogy and cultural studies. But, in fact, one of the reasons why people go to cultural leisure centers is the interest to communicate and obtain information. Exchanging information with each other is a characteristic of all people. Since ancient times, people have gathered in different places of villages and cities to discuss various events and individuals. They have "gossiped" in a good or bad way. This process, which everyone perceives as gossip, actually arose from the need of each individual to exchange information.

As the means of information have increased in the village or city, the exchange of ideas has also increased. International information has been added to the information related to domestic and local activities. Gradually, the geopolitical space of information has increased, and people's comprehension activity has expanded. The expansion of comprehension

activity has enriched the content of information exchange and created new means for the realization of this goal in a cultural form. So, cultural institutions have actually performed the function of informing people with their entertaining events that are informative in nature. Comprehension activity is one of the main components of information exchange. This type of activity also develops in two directions during the communication process. The first stage is the process of imparting and assimilating information to each other. Imparting information to each other takes place mainly during the process of personalized communication. However, the process of information transmission also takes place during lectures, debates, events and circles. The data budget increases in both cases. It is exchanged at the same time. The information exchange creates topics for the creation of new discussions. A new heuristic activity of each individual is formed, i.e. information exchange deepens thinking, creates a heuristic activity environment for acquiring new knowledge.

The information exchange in communication does not result only in the collection of information. A person who engages in information exchange does not avoid to evaluate the nature of the discussed, seen and heard events. Each individual evaluates the environment surrounding him, social events, his own and other people's behavior as an object of discussion. Of course, this evaluation activity deepens the received information, strengthens the memory, creates an opportunity to compare events and ideas, to think again, to check the correctness of the decisions and conclusions.

The mentioned fact confirms once again that as information exchange, which is one of the main factors of communication, develops with all its components, the professional characteristics of individuals also increase, they acquire special habits and moral qualities. At the same time, new qualitative changes occur in the life of each individual. An individual who analyzes the work, deeds and moral quality of others will inevitably be critical of himself. Especially, he gets the opportunity to compare the good or bad aspects of his artistic image with his own characteristics. He also engages in self-evaluation through this comparison. After that, practical changes occur in his life. A struggle between good and evil emerges in his nature. Depending on the influence of the environment in which the individual lives, the good aspects crowd out the bad aspects gradually. So, many qualities of an individual change and renew in the process of experimental activity.

The directions of renewal are also different. People change in a bad way depending on the environment and circumstances. The Soviet empire also changed the nature of our people constantly under the name of international upbringing and carried out “mangurt” (a person who has forgotten the past, abandoned national traditions, etc.) propaganda. The peoples and nations under the slavery of the empire were separated from their ancestry, language, customs and traditions.

After Azerbaijan became independent, a new process of information exchange began in the minds of our people. There was a need to get rid of the false information that the communist regime “injected” into our brains. The impact of communication and interaction changed. The period of transition from one structure to another renewed the content and functional side of the activity. The tendency of people to study the historical roots and to follow the customs and traditions that have been preserved in the memory and everyday life of the people for centuries has strengthened. The information exchange, which was denied in former times, was brought into the discussion arena again.

Many Russian authors mention information exchange as a communicative interaction form of communication. A.G.Andreyev, A.V.Telyuk, M.S.Kagan, N.Y.Arefina and others did not agree with this concept. They believed that defining communication as the information exchange narrows its scope. We consider information exchange as one of the components and aspects of communication in our research.

“Communication” is an English word, the literal meaning of which is understood as “imparting”, “informing”. Communication is also translated as “come together”, “to interact” [5, p. 169]. However, communication is more commonly understood as a “means of contact”. Information exchange is one of the components of communication and can be understood as a means of contact.

Spiritual-cultural communication is a necessary way of realizing spiritual life. People who communicate mutually enrich each other during the process of communication. The ability to participate in communicative processes does not depend only on the emotional richness and intellectual level of the individual spiritual life of people. The effectiveness and practical character of that participation often determines the moral climate of the society. Some people see the richness of cultural life in the diversity of spiritual communication [1, p.118].

The information exchange between individuals during communication is not only the exchange of imagination, ideas, interests and views. There is also an exchange of feelings, deeds and behaviors. This aspect conveys the interactive aspect of communication.

A second aspect is called the “perpetual aspect”. The perpetual aspect is understood as mutual comprehension and solidarity between the sides.

As a result, it can be concluded that the mechanism of information exchange, i.e. its acquisition and transmission depend on the form of communication. The results arising from the requirements of the information exchange are as following:

- the ability to make contracts and relationships with other people;
- the ability to achieve solidarity;
- the ability to make the companion change their position;
- the ability to get into different roles [5];
- the ability to maintain internal autonomy during interaction.

This mentioned aspect is the main factor that regulates the level of communicative activity of each individual and can lead to a new level of quality. At the same time, it is the ability to demonstrate and continue own will and principle. A strong-willed person tries not to deviate from the rules of behavior when doing any work. Following the rules of this behavior allows a human to see the result of his behaviors. As a human becomes morally mature and perfect, he tends to do good deeds. Moral deed is based on consciousness and will.

Even when people with weak will exchange information with each other, the flaws in their morals and behavior are quickly revealed. They are not cultured to conduct a dialogue, accept criticism and respond to shortcomings with self-control. But, the information exchange environment of communication forces him to judge himself sooner or later. Especially, people who are able to judge themselves can always rise to the top of wisdom.

Conclusion. As you know, communication includes the diversity of spiritual and material forms of human activity, and this aspect is its important requirement. It is no secret that the relationship between personalities and individuals is more important today. Modern socio-psychology proves that the emotional relationship is very necessary for a human and at the same time is the main provider of the comprehensive development of communication. It is impossible to understand and share the joys and sorrows of others without an emotional relationship. Communication is the most important

feature of a human's emotional state. As a rule, communication is emotional from tenderness to rudeness, from love to hate. Therefore, people not only exchange information with each other, but also express their attitudes to each other during the process of communication. As a result, a special environment that is desirable and important for them is formed around the people who interact with each other. However, while communicating, human is able to look at himself and his behavior from the outside through the eyes of others. The ability to see and analyze own behavior gives each individual the opportunity to evaluate their behaviors and correct their mistakes in time. The individual who acquires this ability can often foresee the consequences of his behaviors. Such communication becomes a source of free information. The individual during communication increases the potential of comprehension in all kinds of relationships, acquires more comprehensive knowledge. When the comprehension potential increases, the quality level of information exchange also increases. Time is also saved when comprehension potential is increased. So, communication becomes a means of qualitative transmission of information.

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Gülçin Kazımi (Azərbaycan)

ÜNSİYYƏT PROSESİNDƏ MILLİ ÖZÜNÜDƏRKETMƏ VƏ İNFORMASIYA MÜBADİLƏSİNİN ROLU

Son otuz ildə Azərbaycan müstəqil dövlət kimi yeni ictimai, siyasi, iqtisadi quruluşa qədəm qoymuş, onun mədəni həyatında da bir sıra dəyişikliklər baş vermiş, çevik demokratik fəaliyyət mərhələsi başlanmışdır. Məhz yeni cəmiyyətdə demokratik əsasların üstünlük təşkil etməsi insanlar arasındakı əlaqələrin sərhədlərini genişləndirmiş, mədəni ünsiyyətin forma və mahiyyətində də yeniləşmə aparılmasının labüdlüyünü aşkarlamışdır. Azərbaycanın ictimai-siyasi və mədəni həyatında baş verən bu dəyişikliklər ünsiyyətin

sosial-psixoloji mahiyyətini də dəyişdi. Yeni cəmiyyətin yaranması və onun insanlara bəxş etdiyi demokratik prinsiplər mədəni ünsiyyət sahəsində mövcud olan məhdudiyətlərin aradan qaldırılmasına səbəb oldu. Məhz bu məhdudiyətlərin aradan qaldırılması ümumbəşəri mədəni sərvətlərdən daha geniş istifadə olunmasına mənəvi zəmin yaratdı, mədəni ünsiyyətin tarixi-ənənəvi cəhətlərdən bərpa edilməsi problemlərinin aktuallığını üzə çıxartdı. Məlum oldu ki, insanların əsrlər boyu inkişaf etmiş milli, dini ünsiyyət formaları və başqa mənəvi dəyərləri böyük tərbiyəvi əhəmiyyət kəsb edir, mahiyyət etibarı ilə müasir dövrdə də insanlar arasında mədəni ünsiyyət əlaqələrinin genişlənməsi üçün yeni sosial psixoloji zəmin yaradır.

Açar sözlər: kommunikasiya, ünsiyyət, informasiya mübadiləsi, qarşılıqlı təsiretmə, özünüdərkətmə.

Гюльчин Казыми (Азербайджан)

РОЛЬ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО САМООСОЗНАНИЯ И ОБМЕНА ИНФОРМАЦИЕЙ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБЩЕНИЯ

Азербайджан вступил в новый общественно-политический и экономический строй как независимое государство, в его культурной жизни произошли некоторые изменения, за последние тридцать лет начался этап гибкой демократической деятельности. Тем более, что преобладание демократических начал в новом обществе расширило границы отношений между людьми и выявило необходимость новаторства в форме и сущности культурного общения. Эти изменения в общественно-политической и культурной жизни Азербайджана изменили и социально-психологический характер общения. Появление нового общества и демократические принципы, которые оно дало людям, привели к устранению существовавших ограничений в сфере культурного общения. Именно устранение этих ограничений создало нравственную почву для более широкого использования универсальных культурных ресурсов, выявило актуальность проблем восстановления культурной коммуникации с исторической и традиционной точек зрения. Стало ясно, что складывавшиеся веками народные формы национального, религиозного общения и другие духовные ценности имеют большое воспитательное значение и создают принципиально новую социально-психологическую основу для расширения культурного общения людей в современную эпоху.

Ключевые слова: общение, коммуникабельность, информационный обмен, взаимодействие, самосознание.